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RESULTS OF CHILDREN'S BRAIN TUMOR TREATMENT OVER A TEN-YEAR PERIOD AT THE INSTITUTE OF ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY OF SERBIA

Dragana Stanic^{1,2}, Jelena Bokun^{1,2}, Marija Popovic-Vukovic¹,
Predrag Filipovic¹, Borko Nidzovic¹, Marina Nikitovic^{1,2}

¹*Institute of Oncology and Radiology of Serbia*

²*Faculty of Medicine, University of Belgrade*

Abstract

Objective: This study aimed to evaluate the characteristics of children with primary brain tumors, the effectiveness of treatment modalities, and to detect factors related to the outcome.

Methods: A detailed analysis was performed on a series of 173 pediatric patients treated in a referral institution, the Institute of Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, between 2007 and 2016, based on their clinical, histological, treatment, and follow-up data.

Results: Mean survival time of all children was 94.5 months. 2-, 5- and 10-year overall survival probabilities were 68.8%, 59.4%, and 52.8%, respectively. Patients with supratentorial tumors had longer survival than patients with infratentorial and tumors in both compartments. Children with unknown histopathology and high-grade glioma had a shorter life than embryonal tumors, ependymoma, and low-grade glioma. Survival of children who underwent gross total resection was significantly longer than the children with lesser degrees of resection. Patients with no evidence of disease upon admission to our Institute lived longer than patients with local residual disease and disseminated disease. By the univariate analysis, factors predicting poor outcome were the presentation of disease with hormonal abnormalities, tumor location, NFS, and the extent of the disease, while the factors predicting a better outcome were age, presentation of the disease with neurological deficit, and type of resection. By the multivariate analysis, the extent of the disease remained the only strong adverse risk factor for survival.

Conclusions: Children with brain tumors have a chance for long-term survival. With a trained and dedicated multidisciplinary team, adequate outcomes can be achieved.

Keywords: brain tumors, treatment, children, pediatric

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